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AN APPROACH TO THE CONCEPT OF KRIMI (MICROBES)

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda exist since ancient time and since then Acharya knew that healthy state of body can be disturbed by the external minute infectious organisms known as Krimi (Microbes). Explanation of Krimi(Microbes) is found in different Samhitas and Krimi (Microbes) word is also mentioned in Atharva Veda. Acharya's have mentioned description of etiologies, types & number, habitat, nomenclature, morphology, clinical conditions and treatment of Krimi(Microbes). In Shabdakalpadruma Krimi(Microbes) is derived from word Bhrame Samprasarane which means Pada or legs. Krimi(Microbes) is mainly of two types Bahya Krimi (External Microbes) which is two in number and Abhyantara Krimi(Internal Microbes) which is divided into three types Raktaja Krimi, Shleshmaja or Kaphaja and Purishaja. Acharya have mentioned Krimirogas (Microbial Infections) which occur due to Krimi(Microbes). All microorganisms like virus, bacteria, and parasites can be included under the title Krimi(Microbes). Some researcher have correlated Krimi(Microbes) with certain microbes explained in modern medical science. Based on the explanation available on Krimi(Microbes) it is slightly difficulty to correlate it with microbes told in modern medical science. In Allopathic science there are two branches separately studied for worms and microbes which is known as helminthology and microbiology respectively but in Ayurveda Krimi(Microbes) is mentioned for both worm and microbes. Mainly it will result in skin disorders and ailments of gastrointestinal system. Acharya have explained Shodhana(Purification method) as a basic treatment of Krimi(Microbes) and also explained about three folded treatment for Krimiroga(Microbial Infections) which is Apatarpana,Prakritivighata and Nidana Parivarjana. Here, an attempt is made to understand the Krimi(Microbes) in current perspective.

Key words : Krimi, Abhyantara Krimi, Microbes, Shodhana

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda exist since ancient time and since then Acharya knew that healthy state of body can be disturb by the external minute infectious organisms known as Krimi (Microbes). In Ayurveda explanation of Krimi is found in Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita and Astanga Hridaya and Astanga Sangraha many other Samhita. The word Krimi is derived from Bhrame Samprasarane which means Pada or legs(1). It is of two types first one is Bahya Krimi(External Microbes) and other is Abhyantara Krimi(Internal Microbes) which is further divided into Raktaja, Shleshmaja or Kaphaja and

Purishaja(2). Each type is further divided into different subtypes according to different Acharya although all Acharya have mentioned total 20 types of Krimi(Microbes). This Krimi habitat different part of the body and causes different ailments of gastrointestinal system and alimentary system.

Existence of Krimi is mentioned in Atharva Veda. In Atharva Veda they have divided it into two types Drishta and Adrishta type meaning visible and invisible(3).

Table no.01 Showing types and numbers of *Krimi*

Name of Acharya	Bahya Krimi	Kaphaja
Charaka(4)	2	7
Sushruta(5)		6
Vagabhatta(6)	2	7
Madhavakara (7)	2	7

Name of Acharya	Purishaja	Raktaja	Total No.
Charaka(4)	5	6	20
Sushruta(5)	7	7	20
Vagabhatta(6)	5	6	20
Madhavakara (7)	5	6	20

Figure no.01 showing types of *Raktaja Krimi*

Figure no.01 showing types of *Raktaja Krimi*

Figure no.02 showing types of *Purishaja Krimi*

Figure no.03 showing types of *Kaphaja Krimi*

Causative factor: The causative factor for Bahya Krimi(External Microbes) is Mrija Varjana means unhygienic and dirty habits. Causative factors of Abhyantara Krimi is Ajeerna Bhojana (Intake before digestion of previous meal), regular intake of Madhura(sweet) and Amla Rasa(Sour), consumption of Drava(liquid) substance, Guda, Virudhha Bhojana etc and Viharaja factors are Diwaswapna (Day sleeping) and Avyayama.(12)

Bahya Krimi:

Bahya Krimi samuthan is said to be Mrujavarjana (Unhygienic) and Sthana(Habitat) is Keshha(Hairs on scalp), Smashru (Beard), Lomapakshma (Eye lashes). These microbes are very minute (Anu), like Tila Akruiti (Sesame) with Bahupada(Multiple podia). These Krimi is blackish white in color.⁽¹³⁾

Raktaja Krimi:

Raktaja Krimi occurs due to factors which are responsible for Kushta Vyadhi. These Krimi (Microbes) resides in Raktavahini Dhamini. These Krimi are Anu (Atomic), Vrutta (Oval), lacks organ of motility(Apada) and invisible due to minute size(Sukshmatvat Adrushya). These are coppery red in colour and might be reddish or blackish.⁽¹⁴⁾

Kaphaja Krimi:

The causative factors are Kapha Prakopa Nidana's (Causative factor) like consumption of meat, bean, jiggery, milk, curd, fish, Kusumbha and intake of Ajirna(Uncooked), Klina (wet), Sankirna (Contaminated) and Virudhha (Antagonistic) and Asatmya Ahara (Incompatible). These Krimi reside in gastrointestinal tract with shape of Pruthu(Oval), Bradhna (Flat and Thick), Vrutta Parinah(Spherical flat), Anu (Minute), Dirgha(Long) and Tantuvat(thready).⁽¹⁵⁾ Purishaja Krimi : The causative factors are ingestion of Masha(bans), Pishtanna(floured grains) and raw vegetables are responsible for the infection. These Krimi reside in Pakwashaya and are Sukshma (Minute), Vrutta (Oval), Parinaha (Flat), Deergha (Long) and Urnashu Shanka (Long woolen fibres). Some are thick, oval and flat. These are whitish or blackish, greenish and yellowish in colour⁽¹⁶⁾ These Krimi(Microbes) is treated by adopting three treatment protocol which are Apakarshana,

Prakriti Vighatana and Nidana Parivarjana. Apakarshana is said to be first line of treatment and it expulse Krimi and Malas from the host by mechanical or therapeutic method. In Prakriti Vighatana treatment procedure like Abhyanga(Massage), Sweda(Sudation), Pradeha etc and some internal medicines are advised which destroys the favorable environment of Krimi. Third treatment is Nidana Parivarjana which is avoiding causative factors of Krimi⁽¹⁷⁾.

DISCUSSION

These Krimi's are hard to correlate with microbes due to limited information but it can be compared by knowing their habitat, morphological character and sign & symptoms they produce. Bahya Krimi(External microbes) can be correlated to louse (head, body, pubic) and eggs of louse which stick to the root of hair. Raktaja Krimi are minute and reside in Raktavahini Dhamani and produce disease like Kushta (Skin Disease). There are few microbes which reside in blood stream those are staphylococcus which could cause folliculitis, boils and abscess. Streptococcus Pyogens⁽¹⁸⁾ which causes Erysipels, impetigo, pyoderma and subcutaneous infections like cellulitis. Fungi like candida albicans, tinea corporis, tinea imbricate, tinea cruris, tinea barbae, tinea capitis which produces variety of localized skin infection in scalp, body and nail⁽¹⁹⁾. Kaphaja Krimi are present in upper part of the gut and when increase in number they travel through upper and lower gut. Characteristic of these Krimi are thick, flat, elongated, rounded & ring like and causes symptoms like nausea, salivation, anorexia, indigestion, fever etc.

Parasites like Anyclostoma duodenale⁽²⁰⁾ causes abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea with blood, anemia. Taenia solium & taenia saginata causes nausea, abdominal discomfort, and hunger pain, chronic indigestion etc. *Purishaja Krimi* resides in lower gut and when increase in number travel through upper & lower GIT. Their size varies from minute to macroscopic and causes symptoms like diarrhea, emaciation, pallor, horripilation, perianal itching etc. Bacteria like Vibrio cholera, E.coli, Salmonella, Shigella⁽²¹⁾ causes symptoms like diarrhea, dysentery, enteric fever, gastro enteritis. Virus like rota virus, astro virus, adeno virus causes symptoms like severe diarrhea and lethargy. Fungi like candida albicans causes diarrhea.

CONCLUSION

Concept of *Krimi* is explained in *Veda* and in many *Samhita's* with its causative factors, nomenclature, habitat, morphology and its clinical symptoms but even with available information about *Krimi* it is difficult to correlate with microbes explained in modern medical science. Branches like helminthology and microbiology explains in detail about worms & microbes and if more detail description on *Krimi* is available then exact correlation with these worms and microbes can be done. Hence more research should be done to understand *Krimi* and its exact correlation with worms and microbes of modern medical science.

REFERENCES

- 1) Dev RK. Shabdakalpadruma Vol. -2. V a r a n a s i . Chaukhambha Sanskrit Series office.1967:178
- 2) Tripathi BN.Charaka Samhita. Vol 1.Varanasi. Chaukhambha Surbharati Publication 2013:340
- 3) Shashtri RG.Vedomain Ayurved.Delhi. Jamna Printing works.1956:55
- 4) Tripathi BN.Charaka Samhita. Vol 1.Varanasi. Chaukhambha Surbharati Publication 2013:712-713
- 5) Shashtri KA.Shushruta Samhita vol 2 (Uttartantra). Varanasi.Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan.2012:400
- 6) Gupta.AD.Atanga Hridaya (Nidanasthana).Varanasi. Chaukhambha Prakashan. 2009:373
- 7) Tripathy BN.Madhava Nidana (Roga Vinischaya Madhukosa).Vol-2.Varanasi.Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan. 2009:373
- 8) Tripathi RD.Charaka Samhita Vol-1. (Vimanasthana). Delhi.Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan.2011:604
- 9) Tripathi RD.Charaka Samhita Vol-1. (Vimanasthana). Delhi.Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan. 2011:604
- 1) Thakral KK.Sushruta Samhita.Varanasi. Chaukhambha Orientalia.2023:516
- 2) Rao.B.M.Astanga Hridaya. (Nidanasthana). Varanasi. Chaukhambha Vishwabharati.2016:125
- 3) Byadgi PS.Madhav Nidana Vol-1.New Delhi. Chaukhambha Publications.2021:114
- 4) Tripathi RD.Charaka Samhita Vol-1. (Vimanasthana). Delhi.Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan.2011:605
- 5) Tripathi RD.Charaka Samhita Vol-1. (Vimanasthana). Delhi.Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan.2011:605
- 6) Tripathi RD.Charaka Samhita Vol-1. (Vimanasthana). Delhi.Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan.2011:605
- 7) Tripathi RD.Charaka Samhita Vol-1. (Vimanasthana). Delhi.Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan.2011:606
- 8) Tripathi RD.Charaka Samhita Vol-1. (Vimanasthana). Delhi.Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan.2011:607
- 9) Paniker C.K.J.Textbook of Microbiology.7th Edition. chennai.orient longman pvt ltd.2005:197
- 10)Paniker C.K.J.Textbook of Microbiology.7th Edition. chennai.orient longman pvt ltd.2005:208
- 11)Chakraborty P. Textbook of Medical Parasitology.2nd edition. kolkata.New central book agency(p)ltd.2013:158
- 12)Paniker C.K.J.Textbook of Microbiology.7th Edition. chennai.orient longman pvt ltd.2005:309,275,287

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